

Learning Mathematics Using Core Learning Model to Support Numeracy Skills and Learning Achievement of Junior High School Students

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 27 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Maryam Pratiwi Azra</p> <p>KEYWORDS: CORE Model; Numeracy; Learning Achievement</p>	<p>Numeracy skills and learning achievement are important aspects in mathematics learning that support students' readiness to face the challenges of the modern era. However, in reality, many junior high school students still show low and suboptimal numeracy skills and learning achievement. Therefore, a learning model is needed that can facilitate students' numeracy skills and learning achievement. The objectives of this study were to 1) analyse the effect of mathematics learning using CORE model on students' numeracy skills, 2) analyse the effect of mathematics learning using CORE model on students' learning achievement. This type of research is pseudo-experimental research with quantitative approach. The subjects of this research were 23 students of SMP 3 Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta. Data collection techniques in this study used tests which included: 1) numeracy skill test, 2) mathematics learning achievement test. The data analysis technique in this research is hypothesis testing using paired sample t-test. The results of this study showed that: 1) learning mathematics using CORE model can support numeracy skills, 2) learning using CORE model can improve students' mathematics learning achievement.</p>

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a cognitive method that aims to improve critical, rational, systematic, logical, and objective thinking (Hasratuddin, 2015).

Evaluation and measurement of student competence is inevitable to ensure optimal education quality. The success of education begins with the success of learning in the classroom, students' understanding must be higher and creativity in solving a problem is also the main point (Rohmawati, 2015). The focus of learning mathematics in this century is to improve the ability to think critically, master technology, communicate, work together, and connect knowledge with the real world.

Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) is one part of the national assessment (AN) which is a new educational evaluation in Indonesia as a replacement for the National Exam (Ujian Nasional, UN) in the independent learning curriculum (Whalery, 2022). AKM is specifically designed to measure thinking and reasoning competencies so that students are able to use higher-order thinking skills so that they can achieve 21st century skills in the form of critical thinking, problem solving,

creativity, communication skills, ability to work collaboratively (Andiani, 2020). There are two aspects of basic competencies that are emphasised by the AKM, namely reading literacy and numeracy (mathematical literacy) (Kemendikbud, 2020).

Numeracy skills are one of the main objectives in learning mathematics. Numeracy skills are the ability to think by using mathematical concepts, facts, procedures and tools to solve everyday problems in various situations (Kemendikbud, 2020). Numeracy involves the ability to analyse information presented in various forms such as graphs, tables, or diagrams, and use the results of these analyses to predict and make decisions (Alhafits et al., 2023). Numeracy skills focus on the ability to solve, formulate, interpret problems, analyse and give reasons and convey ideas in various forms in everyday life (H. Forgasz et al., 2017). Numeracy skills are very important for students because they are closely related to solving everyday mathematical problems (Pangesti, 2018). However, according to research by Ate & Lede (2022), it is revealed that junior high school students are still lacking in numeracy. Students struggle to understand

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complex mathematical concepts and their inability to absorb information effectively during the learning process (Istiyani et al., 2018).

Furthermore, numeracy skills can affect student learning outcomes which result in student learning achievement. Therefore, one of the aspects that must be improved in learning mathematics is learning achievement. Student learning achievement in mathematics is an important benchmark that reflects the success of learning. Learning achievement can be interpreted as the result of the learning process. Student learning achievement can help teachers know the extent to which the learning objectives have been formulated (Collins & O'Brien, 2003). But in reality, Indonesian students' learning achievement is still low. This is based on data from the national examination results released by the Centre and Assessment of the Ministry of Education and Culture, which states that the average score for mathematics at the junior high school level is 46.56 and at the secondary school level is 42.24 from a range of 0-100. It can be seen that this value has not reached 50% of the overall value. Research by Ardila & Hartanto, (2017) and Nurfitriyani et al., (2020) shows that the majority of students in Indonesia have mathematics learning achievements that are below the minimum completion criteria (KKM).

One of the factors that cause students' numeracy skills and learning achievements are not optimal is the quality of the student learning process. Teachers' efforts to improve the quality of learning are still limited to completing tasks. The reflective process is not visible because teachers use a repetitive approach to learning. This situation results in students being less active in the learning process. As a result, it affects their learning achievement.

The learning model that is expected to provide opportunities for students so that they can achieve the standards of students' mathematical abilities in order to achieve learning objectives and be able to facilitate students in developing numeracy skills and student learning achievement is the CORE learning model. The CORE model encourages students' active participation through discussion and direct involvement. Learning activities using the CORE model have many benefits, including improving student learning outcomes, namely, students are more active in learning, better able to remember concepts or information, more able to develop their own thinking power (Suyatno, 2020). The CORE model helps students understand mathematical concepts better and gives them the ability to apply these ideas in various contexts (Irawan, 2018).

Based on the description above, it is necessary to make an innovation in learning mathematics using the CORE learning model to support students' numeracy skills and learning achievement. This research also intends to: 1)

analyse the effect of mathematics learning using CORE learning model on numeracy skills, 2) analyse the effect of mathematics learning using CORE learning model on learning achievement.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study is quantitative research using experimental method conducted to analyse the effect of learning using CORE learning model to support students' numeracy skills and learning achievement. This research design uses One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design which compares the state of a group before and after being given treatment. The stages in this research start from the planning stage, implementation and application of mathematics learning innovations and evaluation.

The planning stage begins with making observations to the school, compiling learning devices, and compiling instruments to be used. The implementation stage begins with giving a pretest with the aim of seeing the initial ability of students seen from numeracy skills and learning achievement, then giving treatment, namely using the CORE learning model in learning, then to see the effect of the treatment given, a posttest of numeracy skills in the form of essay questions and posttest of learning achievement in the form of multiple choice questions.

This research was conducted at SMP 3 Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta in the academic year 2023/2024. The population used in this study were all seventh grade students. The subjects in this study were class VII.H as many as 23 students. The sampling technique used was cluster random sampling. The variables measured were numeracy skills and learning achievement.

The data collection technique in this study was a test. Data collection through the test technique is done by giving a test instrument consisting of a set of questions / questions to obtain data on student abilities, especially in the cognitive aspect. In this study the authors used pretest and posttest data. "Pretest data is obtained through tests carried out before the treatment is given, in this case the author gives a pretest with flat building material. This pretest data is used to provide an overview of the initial abilities of students before research is conducted or before treatment is given. Posttest data is obtained through tests conducted after the treatment is given at the end of the study, this posttest data is used to determine the description of the final ability / achievement of students' abilities in flat building material.

The instruments in this study were used to obtain data in the form of numeracy tests and student learning achievement. The numeracy test instrument was prepared based on theory and indicators of numeracy achievement. The form of numeracy test instrument used is a description test. Next, the student mathematics learning achievement test instrument was prepared based on the

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basic competencies in learning mathematics flat building material. The form of learning achievement test instrument used is a multiple choice test consisting of 10 questions.

Data analysis in this study includes validity and reliability tests on the instrument, hypothesis testing using the Paired Sample t test and descriptive analysis (mean, standard deviation, maximum score, and minimum score). The criteria for assessing the achievement of basic competencies and numeracy skills as in Table 1.

Table 1. Assessment criteria for numeracy skills and student learning achievement

Interval Score	Category
<20	Very Poor
$21 \leq X \leq 40$	Poor
$41 \leq X \leq 60$	Fair
$61 \leq X \leq 80$	Good
$81 \leq X \leq 100$	Very Good

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After implementing mathematics learning using the CORE learning model in class VII.H SMP 3 Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta, there is an increase in student learning outcomes in terms of basic competencies on flat building material. The results of numeracy achievement are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Numeracy Achievement Results

Statistics	Pre Test	Post Test
	$n_1 = 23$	$n_1 = 23$
Mean Score	22,39	81,08
Standar Deviation	8,7	5,3
Max Score	35	95
Min Score	5	70

Based on the results of the achievement of numeracy skills presented in Table 2, it shows that the average score of the pretest and posttest has increased by 58.69 where the average score obtained during the pretest shows 22.39 and the posttest average score shows 81.08 which is in the interval $81 \leq x \leq 100$ with a very good category.

From the results of the table presented, it also shows that there is a significant effect of the CORE learning model on the achievement of numeracy skills. This result is directly proportional to the research conducted by Wahyuni (2017); Humaira (2015) which shows that the CORE learning model is appropriate for improving numeracy skills. The research revealed the objectives of the CORE learning model which had a positive impact on

several aspects of numeracy, namely problem solving, concept understanding and critical thinking of students." Furthermore, the results of learning achievement presented in Table 3 show that the CORE learning model can support mathematics learning with a good category.

Table 3. Learning Achievement Results

Statistics	Pre Test	Posttest
	$n_1 = 23$	$n_1 = 23$
Mean Score	28,69	70
Standar Deviation	6,79	10,21
Max Score	40	90
Min Score	20	50

Based on the results of learning achievement presented in Table 3, it shows that the average score of the pretest and posttest has increased by 41.31 where the average score obtained during the pretest shows 28.69 for the posttest average score shows 70 which is in the interval $61 \leq x \leq 80$ with a good category.

Based on the results of the table presented, it also shows that there is a significant effect of the CORE learning model on student learning achievement. The results of this study are directly proportional to the research conducted by Ningsih (2020) which shows that the CORE learning model is appropriate for improving student learning achievement.

Furthermore, the results of the implementation of mathematics learning using the CORE learning model obtained data presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Implementation of learning using the CORE learning model

	Meeting	Presentation
	Teacher	Student
1	90.6%	90.6%
2	96.7%	96.7%
3	100%	100%
Mean	95.7%	95.7%

Data on the results of learning implementation using the CORE learning model was obtained from the mathematics teacher who acted as an observer to observe learning activities in the classroom.

Based on Table 4, it is obtained that the average for the implementation of teacher and student activities is 95.7% which indicates the implementation of learning is very good.

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Furthermore, the results of data analysis on the achievement of basic competencies (KD), competency achievement indicators (IPKD) and learning achievement with normality test are presented in Figure 1.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		23
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	9.38595361
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.145
	Positive	.145
	Negative	-.139
Test Statistic		.145
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

a. Test distribution is Normal.
 b. Calculated from data.
 c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Figure 1. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

In Figure 1, it can be seen that the sig value for the data is 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, so it can be said that the data is normally distributed.

Furthermore, the results of data analysis on the achievement of basic competencies (KD), indicators of competency achievement (IPKD) and learning achievement with paired sample test are presented in Figure 2.

Paired Samples Test

Pair	Pretest-Posttest	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
1	Pretest-Posttest	-41.204	9.878	2.018	-45.486	-37.118	-20.467	22	.000

Figure 2. Paired Sample Test

In Figure 2, it can be seen that the sig value for the data is 0.000, which means it is smaller than 0.05, so H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, which means that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test learning outcomes/achievement using the inquiry learning model in class VII.H. So it can be concluded that the learning process with a problem solving approach with an inquiry learning model can improve the achievement of KD, IPKD and learning achievement on the material of flat buildings.

Furthermore, the results of data analysis of numeracy skills show an average posttest score of 81.08 which is in the interval $x > 74.9$ with a very high category, so it can be concluded that the learning process with the CORE learning model can support the improvement of students' numeracy skills on flat building material.

From the results of the analysis presented, it shows that there is a significant effect of the CORE learning model

on student learning outcomes in terms of the achievement of basic competency tests conducted. It can be seen in Table 3 that students' learning achievement has increased after using the CORE learning model.

These results are in line with the research of Loka et al., (2020) which revealed that the average value of student learning outcomes was better using the CORE learning model. Furthermore, research conducted by Retnowati & Aqiila (2017) states that the CORE learning model is better than the CORE learning model. CORE can develop/improve student learning achievement.

The implementation of mathematics learning in this study is very good, it can be seen from the percentage results that are displayed that can make students actively involved in the learning process. As stated by Trisnowali & Aswina (2019) that the CORE learning model has a positive influence including an increase in students after learning, namely students are active in learning, training students' memory of a concept or information, training students' thinking about a problem, and providing innovative learning experiences to students.

The CORE model encourages students' active participation in learning. The CORE model is a learning model that involves discussion and engages students (Calfie & Miller, 2004). The CORE model combines four important components of constructivism, namely students connect what they know, organize what they know, give them the opportunity to reflect on what they can, and allow them to be able to expand what they know (Curwen et al., 2010).

In general, this research is in accordance with the research of Susilowaty & Marpaung (2018); Sari & Waluya (2023); Anggraeni et al (2023) that the application of the CORE learning model supports numeracy skills and has an impact on student achievement.

The advantage of the CORE model is that it is able to develop activeness and provide learning experiences to students so that learning is more meaningful, in accordance with Suharto (2014) learning with the CORE model is a learning model with a discussion method based on constructivism theory where the main constructivist concept is that students actively develop knowledge for themselves.

In addition, according to Nelwati et al. (2020), the CORE learning model is able to develop critical thinking as well as problem-solving skills, because this model involves students as thinkers while educators as mediators, facilitators, and motivators.

Through this CORE learning model, it can be an option for teachers to develop more active learning activities for students to build their own knowledge in order to optimize student learning outcomes and mathematics abilities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that there is an effect of learning mathematics using the CORE learning model on students' numeracy skills. CORE learning model can support to improve students' numeracy skills. Furthermore, there is an effect of mathematics learning using the CORE learning model on student learning achievement. Student learning outcomes have increased which has an impact on learning achievement in terms of basic competencies achieved.

Based on the research results and conclusions that have been presented, there are several suggestions for further relevant research: teachers can apply the CORE learning model to improve student learning achievement which has an impact on learning achievement in terms of basic competencies in each material, can develop the CORE learning model for other mathematics materials.

REFERENCES

1. Alhfits, R., Rohana, R., & Hera T. (2023). Analysis of Numeration Ability Form The Results of The Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) nn Class V Students of at SD Negeri 101 Palembang. *Edumaspul: Journal of Education*, 7(2), 5469-5479. <https://doi.org/10.33487/edumaspus.v7i2.7349>
2. Andiani, D. (2020). Concept and Implementation of Minimum Competency Assessment in Improving 21st Century Skills. Jakarta: Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.
3. Anggraeni, E., Rulyansah, A., Setyowati, T. D., & Rahayu, P. (2023, June). Improving Student Learning Outcomes with the Core Model on Water Cycle Material at SDN 23 Gresik. In *Proceedings of the National Conference for Ummah (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 338-342)*.
4. Ardila, A., & Hartanto, S. (2017). Factors that influence the low mathematics learning outcomes of iskandar muda batam mts students. *PYTHAGORAS: Journal of Mathematics Education Study Program*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.33373/pythagoras.v6i2.966>
5. Ate, D., & Lede, Y. K. (2022). Analysis of Class VIII Students' Ability in Solving Numeracy Literacy Problems. *Journal of Scholarship: Journal of Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 472-483. <https://doi.org/10.31004/cendekia.v6i1.1041>
6. Calfee, R., & Miler, R. G. (2004). Making Thinking Visible National Science Education Standards.
7. Collins, J. W., & O'Brien, N. P. (2003). The Greenwood dictionary of education. Wesport: Greenwood Publishing Group, Inc.
8. Curwen, M. S., Miller, R. G., White-Smith, K. A., & Calfee, R. C. (2010). Increasing Teachers' Metacognition Develops Students' Higher Learning During Content Area Literacy Instruction: Findings From The Read-Write Cycle Project. *Issues In Theacer Education*, 19(2).
9. Forgasz, H. J., Leder, G., & Hall, J. (2017). Numeracy across the curriculum in Australian schools: Teacher education students' and practicing teachers' views and understandings of numeracy. *Numeracy*, 10(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1936-4660.10.2.2>
10. Hasratuddin. (2015). Why should we learn math? Medan: Perdana Publishing.
11. Humaira, T. (2015). Improving Mathematical Comprehension and Problem Solving Ability, as well as Habist Of Mind of Mts Students Through CORE Learning Using Cognitive Conflict Strategy. Thesis, Unpublished, University of Education Indonesia, Bandung.
12. Irawan, B. P. (2018). The Effect of CORE Learning Model (Connecting, Organizing, Reflecting, Extending) on Concept Understanding Ability and Mathematical Reasoning Ability of Vocational High School Students. *Journal Of Mathematics Science And Education*, 1(1), 38-54. <https://doi.org/10.31540/jmse.v1i1.132>
13. Istiyani, R., Muchyidin, A., & Raharjo, H. (2018). Analysis of student misconception on geometry concepts using three-tier diagnostic test. *Journal of Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 37(2). <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v37i2.14493>
14. Loka, J. M., Wena, I. M., & Wibawa, K. A. (2020, July). The Effect of Implementing the Core Learning Model on Mathematics Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students of SMP Widya Sakti Denpasar. In *Proceedings of Mahasaraswati National Seminar on Mathematics Education*.
15. Ministry of Education and Culture. (2020). Guidelines for Implementing National Assessment: Minimum Competency Assessment and Character Survey. Jakarta: Ministry of Education and Culture.
16. Ministry of Education and Culture. (2020a). AKM Question Development Design. Research and Development and Bookkeeping Agency of the Ministry of Education and Culture.

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17. Nelwati, S., Febrianto, D., & Zeliana, S. (2020). Analysis of the Effect of the Connecting Organizing Reflecting Extending (CORE) Learning Model on Science Learning in Class V SD/MI. Tarbiyah Al-Awlad: *Journal of Elementary Islamic Education*, 10(1), 103-112. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jpm.v15i2.1475>
18. Nurfitriyanti, M., Rosa, N. M., & Nursaadah, F. P. (2020). The influence of critical thinking skills, adversity quotient and locus of control on mathematics learning achievement. *JKPM (Journal of Mathematics Education Studies)*, 5(2), 263-272. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30998/jkpm.v5i2.5929>
19. Pangesti, F. T. P. (2018). Developing Numeracy Literacy in Mathematics Learning with HOTS Questions. *Indonesian Digital Journal Of Mathematics And Education*, 5(9), 566–575. <https://Idealmathedu.P4tkmatematik A.Org>
20. Rahayu, D., & Kusuma, A. (2019). Strategy to Improve Students' Mathematical Ability through Innovative Learning. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 3(1), 45-56.
21. Retnowati, E., & Aqiila, A. (2017). The effectiveness of paired grouping strategy in CORE model mathematics learning. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, (1), 13-23. <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v35i1.12628>
22. Rohmawati, D. (2015). Educational Evaluation: Concepts and Applications in Learning. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
23. Sari, Y. E., & Waluya, S. B. (2023, December). Systematic Literature Review: CORE Learning Model on Students' Mathematical Critical Thinking Ability. In SEMANTIK: Proceedings of the National Seminar on Mathematics Education (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 488-498).
24. Suharto, B., Setyowati, A., & Utami, N. (2014). Implementation of CORE Learning Model to Improve Student Activity and Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 3(1), 112-119.
25. Susilowaty, N., & Marpaung, M. S. (2018, October). Effect of CORE learning models with cognitive-conflict strategy towards the mathematics problem solving and anxiety of junior high school students. In *Abstract Proceedings International Scholars Conference (Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 289-289)*. <https://doi.org/10.35974/isc.v6i1.1274>
26. Suyatno, S. (2020). Benefits of CORE Learning Model in Improving Student Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(1), 20-30.
27. Trisnowali, A., & Aswina, A. (2019). The Influence of the CORE (Connecting, Organizing, Reflecting, and Extending) Learning Model on the Learning Outcomes of Class X Students. *Didaktika: Journal of Education*, 13(1), 43–55. <http://dx.doi.org/10.30863/didaktika.v13i1.315>
28. Vhalery, M. (2022). Minimum Competency Assessment: Concept and Implementation in the Independent Learning Curriculum. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
29. Wahyuni, S. (2017). The Effectiveness of the CORE (Connecting, Organizing, Reflecting, Extending) Learning Model with Cognitive Conflict Strategy Reviewed from Mathematics Learning Achievement, Critical Thinking Skills and Self-Efficacy. (S2), Yogyakarta State University, Yogyakarta. Retrieved From Eprints.Uny.Ac.Id.